

Friedel-Crafts acylation of furan and thiophene using ytterbium(III) trifluoromethanesulfonate in [BPy][BF₄] ionic liquid

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Friedel-Crafts reactions of furan and thiophene have been catalyzed by ytterbium(III) trifluoromethanesulfonate in [BPy][BF₄] (n-butylpyridinium tetrafluoroborate) ionic liquid to produce intermediates of pharmaceuticals with good yields. The catalyzing system [BPy][BF₄]/Yb(OTf)₃ could be reused.

As the cleaner technologies has become a major concern throughout both industry and academia, the search for alternatives to the most conventional organic solvents has become a hotspot. Ionic liquids, which are entirely composed of ions, are receiving renewed attention for their promise as alternative reaction media¹⁻³. Room temperature ionic liquids have a number of properties which make them suitable alternatives to conventional solvents. They have very low vapour pressure and hence produce virtually no harmful vapours.

Ionic liquids such as [emim]Cl-AlCl₃ (emim = 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazdium)^{3,8} and [emim]I-AlCl₃ (emim = 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazdium)^{3,8,9} have already been used as conventional alternatives to affording pharmaceutical ketones in various Friedel-Crafts reactions³⁻¹⁰. Recently, Song *et al.* have shown that Friedel-Crafts alkylation of aromatics with simple alkenes can readily be performed using Sc(OTf)₃ as catalyst in imidazolium ionic liquids such as [bmin][PF₆]¹⁰. In conventional molecular solvents, Yb(OTf)₃ and a number of other rare earth metal triflates can catalyze Friedel-Crafts alkylation as well as acylation¹¹⁻¹⁷. The amount of the catalyst is catalytic loading. In addition, they can be reused easily. Herein we wish to report Friedel-Crafts acylation of furan and thiophene using Yb(OTf)₃ as catalyst in [BPy][BF₄].

Results and discussion

[BPy][BF₄]/Yb(OTf)₃, as a reusable solvent/catalyst system, can catalyze the Friedel-Crafts reaction of furan and thiophene (Scheme 1). The results are listed in Table 1^a.

The reactions performed smoothly with catalytic amounts of Yb(OTf)₃ using [BPy][BF₄] ionic liquid. We

Scheme 1

found that 0.1 equiv. of catalyst was enough (Entries 1-3), and an excess of Yb(OTf)₃ did not increase the yields. When reducing the amount of Yb(OTf)₃ from 0.1 equiv. to 0.05 equiv., the reaction was slowed noticeably (Entry 3). The reaction of acyl chloride with furan or thiophene performed more faster than that of anhydride (Entries 2, 4). Furthermore, we also found that the reaction of alkyl acyl chloride reacted with furan or thiophene more easily than that of aromatic acyl chloride (Entries 8, 9, 10).

In summary, the feasibility of Yb(OTf)₃ as Lewis acid for Friedel-Crafts acylation in the [BPy][BF₄] ionic liquid has been revealed. Recycling of the solvent/catalyst system was demonstrated in the Experimental.

Experimental

¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian-400 MHz instrument with CDCl₃ as the solvent with TMS as an internal standard. IR spectra were recorded using KBr pellets on a Nicolet Aviator-370 instrument. Melting points were uncorrected. [BPy][BF₄] was prepared from NaBF₄, CH₃(CH₂)₃Br and pyridine¹⁸. Yb(OTf)₃ was prepared from ytterbium oxide and trifluoromethanesulfonic acid in water according to the literature¹⁹. All reagents used are commercially available.

General procedure : [BPy][BF₄] (2 ml) was added into a dry three-neck flask after drying under vacuum for 2 h

Table 1. Friedel-Crafts acylation of furan and thiophene using Yb(OTf)₃ in [BPy][BF₄]

Entry	Yb(OTf) ₃ /eq	Time/h	R ¹	R ²	X	Y	Product	Yield(%) ^b
1	0.1	4	H	CH ₃	OAc	O	3a	79
2	0.2	4	H	CH ₃	OAc	O	3a	79
3	0.05	4	H	CH ₃	OAc	O	3a	65
4	0.1	3	H	CH ₃	Cl	O	3a	87
5	0.1	3	H	CH ₃	OAc	S	3b	86
6	0.1	3	H	CH ₂ CH ₃	Cl	S	3c	84
7	0.1	4	H	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	Cl	S	3d	81
8	0.1	4	H	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	Cl	O	3e	80
9	0.1	10	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	Cl	O	3f	75
10	0.1	10	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	Cl	S	3g	70

^aFor general reaction conditions, see Experimental.

^bBased on furan or thiophene.

with stirring. Hereafter, furan (2 mmol), acetic anhydride (4 mmol) were sequentially added. The mixture was stirred at 50°C for 15 min. After cooling to ambient temperature, [Yb(OTf)₃] (0.2 mmol) was added. The reaction was then stirred at 50°C for 4 h. Upon completion of the reaction, the mixture was extracted with Et₂O. Then the extraction was washed with water (10 ml), aqueous NaHCO₃ (10 ml), water (10 ml × 3). Subsequently the mixture was dried by anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and purified by TLC. The solvent/catalyst system can be reused at 40 °C *in vacuo* for 6 h. **3a**: m.p. 28–30°C (lit.²⁰ 29.3°C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) ppm δ 2.49 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.54–6.55 (1H, m, ArH), 7.19–7.60 (2H, m, ArH); IR (cm⁻¹) 3130, 2926, 1678 (C=O), 1571, 1424, 762. **3b**: m.p. 8–9°C (lit.²¹ 8–10°C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) ppm δ 2.58 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.13–7.15 (1H, m, ArH), 7.64–7.71 (2H, m, ArH); IR (cm⁻¹) 3100, 2955, 2924, 1659 (C=O), 1517, 1414, 719. **3c**: Oil; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) ppm δ 1.23 (3H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz, CH₃), 2.93 (2H, q, *J* 7.3 Hz, CH₂), 7.11–7.14 (1H, m, ArH), 7.61–7.72 (2H, m, ArH); IR (cm⁻¹) 3096, 2978, 2936, 1664 (C=O), 1516, 1416, 723. **3d**: Oil; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) ppm δ 1.00 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.75–1.81 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.88 (2H, t, CH₂), 7.11–7.14 (1H, m, ArH), 7.61–7.72 (2H, m, ArH); IR (cm⁻¹) 3096, 2963, 2931, 2874, 1662 (C=O), 1516, 1416, 723. **3e**: m.p. 10–12°C (lit.²⁰ 11.4°C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) ppm δ 0.99 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.71–1.80 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.80 (2H, t, CH₂), 6.23–6.54 (1H, m, ArH), 7.18–7.19 (1H, m, ArH), 7.58–7.59 (1H, m, ArH); IR (cm⁻¹) 3103, 2958, 2933, 1655 (C=O), 1517, 1416, 724. **3f**: Oil; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) ppm δ 2.44 (3H, t, CH₃), 6.58–6.60 (1H, m, ArH), 7.22–7.31 (3H, m, ArH), 7.70–7.91 (3H, m, ArH); IR (cm⁻¹) 3074, 3038, 2958, 2917, 1624 (C=O), 1603, 1512, 1414, 843, 727. **3g**: m.p. 71–72°C (lit.²² 72°C);

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) ppm δ 2.44 (3H, t, CH₃), 7.14–7.16 (1H, m, ArH), 7.28 (2H, q, *J* 8 Hz, ArH), 7.64–7.70 (2H, m, ArH), 7.77 (2H, q, *J* 8 Hz, ArH); IR (cm⁻¹) 3098, 2922, 1633 (C=O), 1604, 1513, 1414, 883, 723.

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